

The Catalysed Hydration of Nitriles to Amides

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A simple, convenient and inexpensive process for the hydration of nitriles to amides under the influence of manganese-dioxide catalyst has been described. An aqueous solution of the nitrile is employed and the reaction is conducted at moderate temperature with reaction time of a few hours. In most instances nearly quantitative yields of amides are obtained with complete freedom from co-products or side reactions. The I.R. pattern of the catalysts are recorded with a view to correlating these properties with the catalytic activity. A plausible mechanism of the reaction is discussed.

THE hydration of nitriles to amides is catalysed by acids or alkalis in homogeneous phase and has been reported by several investigators^{1,2}. The disadvantages inherent in the use of the alkalis or mineral acids are the formation of the corresponding organic carboxylic acids as by products with the corresponding decrease in the yield of the amides. Further, the product of such reaction would consist of a solution of a mixture of amide, the acid and the catalyst used which necessitates a rather elaborate separation step.

It appeared to us that by the use of water insoluble catalyst of either acidic/basic nature it should be possible to avoid or to minimise the hydrolytic action. With this concept various metals and metallic oxides, alkaline earth carbonates and alkali acid phosphates were tested.

Experimental

The procedure for hydration of pyridine 3-carbonitrile to pyridine 3-carboxamide (Nicotinamide) with manganese dioxide catalyst is shown as an example. The catalyst (1 gm) in 35 ml of water was placed in 250 ml round bottomed flask, and 5 gm of pyridine-3-carbonitrile (99.9% purity) was added. The flask was fitted with an Allihn condenser. The mixture was refluxed vigorously for about five hours. The catalyst was separated by filtration while hot and washed with hot water. The filtrate, admixed with washings, was evaporated on a waterbath. Nicotinamide was obtained as white crystals. The yield was 0.32–5.5 gm (with manganesedioxide catalyst prepared by different methods). The crude amide, although it was fairly pure, was recrystallised from hot water with a small quantity of active charcoal. Mpt. 129.5–130°. Identity was further confirmed by recording an IR spectrum and comparing it with that of an authentic specimen. Experimental conditions employed in different experiments are given in Tables.

Results and Discussion

The nitriles were hydrated to the corresponding amide by the catalytic action of metals like precipitated

copper, nickel, metallic oxides like chromia, vanadia and manganesedioxide, alkaliphosphates and alkaline earth carbonates.

The yields of amides range from 20-95% of theory.

In a few cases, a small quantity of the corresponding acids is obtained by hydrolysis. However, nicotinamide itself is hardly over hydrolysed to nicotinic acid, even when it is refluxed for a long time with a newly prepared catalyst. In general, the hydration to an amide is predominant over other side reactions if the condition of the reaction is suitable. The features of this metal/metaloxide catalysed hydration are peculiar and unlike these of acid or base catalysed hydration.

Table 1 represents the comparative efficiencies of different catalyst systems for the catalysed hydration of 3 & 4 pyridine-carbonitrile to pyridine carboxamide. The highest yield of amide was obtained with manganese dioxide catalyst followed by that with nickel.

Catalysed hydration with nickel as catalyst.

Table 2 represents the results of the experiments carried with nickel as hydration catalyst.

As a whole, electron attracting substituents give better yield of amide as is evident from the Table 2. Thus pyridine 3-&-4-Carbonitriles give a very high yield of amide, the nitrogen atom in the pyridine nucleus having an important electron attracting effect on the cyano group.

A remarkable ortho effect is also observed in this hydration reaction, which has been similarly recognised in the case of acid or alkaline hydration. The yield of amide is more or less diminished with ortho substituted benzonitrile such as ortho-tolunitrile. The reaction velocity becomes slower and often a considerable quantity of starting material is recovered unchanged.

TABLE 1—COMPARATIVE EFFICIENCY OF DIFFERENT CATALYSTS IN THE HYDRATION OF PYRIDINE CARBONITRILE TO PYRIDINE CARBOXAMIDES.

Catalyst	Wt. of Nitrile (gm)	Solvent c.c.	Reaction time (hr.)	Temp. 0°C	Yield of Amide (gm.)	Nitrile Recovered (gm.)
Na (OH)	Pyridine-4-Carbonitrile (5 gm)	50 c.c. N/2 soln.	5	100	5 gm.	Nil.
H ₂ SO ₄	-do- (2 gm)	100 c.c. 90% H ₂ SO ₄ soln.	5	100	1.2 gm.	0.3 gm.
CaCO ₃ (2 gm)	Pyridine-3-Carbonitrile (5 gm.)	40 c.c. water	4	-do-	1.2 gm.	1.5 gm.
Na ₂ HPO ₄ (2 gm.)	-do- (5 gm.)	40 c.c. water	5	-do-	3.6 gm.	0.8 gm.
Li ₂ PO ₄ (2 gm)	-do- (5 gm.)	40 c.c. water	5	-do-	2.2 gm.	—
I.R.A. Amberlite 400	Pyridine-4-Carbonitrile (5 gm)	40 c.c. water	5	-do-	5 gm.	nil.
Activated Iron (2 gm)	Pyridine-4-Carbonitrile (10 gm)	35 c.c. water	5	-do-	2 gm.	5.2 gm.
V ₂ O ₅ (1 gm)	Pyridine-4-Carbonitrile (10 gm)	35 c.c. water	5	-do-	1 gm.	6.3 gm.
MnO ₂ (1 gm)	Pyridine-3-Carbonitrile (5 gm)	35 c.c. water	5	-do-	5.37 gm.	—
Cr ₂ O ₃ (1 gm)	Pyridine-3-Carbonitrile (4 gm)	35 c.c. water	5	-do-	1.3 gm.	0.9 gm.
Ni (1 gm)	Pyridine-3-Carbonitrile (7 gm)	100 c.c. water	10	-do-	5.2 gm.	—
PPTed Cu (1 gm.)	Pyridine-4-Carbonitrile (5 gm)	35 c.c. water	5	-do-	1.07 gm.	—

The purity of Pyridine 3 and 4-Carbonitriles (E Merck) used is 99.9%.

TABLE 2—THE HYDRATION OF NITRILE TO AMIDE WITH NICKEL 5 gm. OF NICKEL USED IN EACH CASE.

Compound	Temperature 100°C.		
	Water c.c.	Reaction time. hr.	Yield of amide (wt. %)
Benzonitrile (E Merck) (5 gm)	80	10	60
<i>o</i> -Tolunitrile (E Merck) (5.5 gm.)	80	12	32
Pyridine-3-Carbonitrile (7 gm)	100	10	70
Pyridine-4-Carbonitrile (5 gm)	100	10	73

Catalysed hydration with manganese dioxide as catalyst

From Table 1 it is observed that of all the catalysts, manganese dioxide exhibited highest selectivity and activity towards hydration of nitriles to amides. Therefore, investigation on different aspects of hydration reaction, so as to optimise the yield of nicotinamide has been carried out with this catalyst.

Effect of methods of preparation of the catalyst :

Table 3 represents the results of the experiments carried out under comparable conditions with manganese dioxide prepared by different methods. It was found

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE EFFICIENCY OF MANGANESE DIOXIDE CATALYSTS PREPARED BY DIFFERENT METHODS. 1 gm OF MnO₂ AND 5 gm. OF PYRIDINE-3-CARBONITRILE USED IN EACH CASE, WATER USED 35 CC, REACTION TIME 5 (FIVE) HOURS, TEMPERATURE 100°C.

Catalyst MnO ₂ , 1 gm.	Yield of Amide gm.	Nitrile recovered gm
F.	5.5	Nil
E.	5.75	1.08
H.	0.32	2.07
I.	5.7	nil.
F. (MnO ₂ from Mn-acetate + H ₂ SO ₄ + K ₂ S ₂ O ₈).		
E. (MnO ₂ from MnCl ₂ .4H ₂ O + KMnO ₄).		
H. (MnO ₂ from Mn(NO ₃) ₂ xH ₂ O heated upto 400°C).		
I. (MnO ₂ from MnSO ₄ + KMnO ₄).		

that two particular methods of preparation* of the catalyst result in the highest selectivity of the catalyst for hydration of pyridine carbonitriles to amides.

Reaction temperature :

The operating temperature is specific to the catalyst and the upper limit to the temperature is determined by the onset of over hydrolysis giving rise to undesirable side products like acids. The lower limit is set by the rate of reaction that can be economic. The temperature range of 60-100° has been investigated with reference to these considerations. It is observed from Table 4 that with increase in temperature, the yield of amide increases and reaches maximum at 100°.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE CONVERSION OF NITRILE TO AMIDE.

Catalyst Manganese dioxide 1 gm. Water 35 c.c.,
Pyridine-3-carbonitrile (5 g.)

No. of obs.	Temp. °C	Nicotinamide (pyridine-3-carboxamide) (Wt. %)
1.	62	48
2.	85	67
3.	90	100
4.	100	114

Reaction time :

Low reaction time favours incomplete hydrolysis, while a high reaction time results in an excess of over-hydrolytic product like acids. It is evident from Table 5 that a reaction time of 5 hrs, is optimum for the catalytic hydration of pyridine 3-carbonitrile to Nicotinamide.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF REACTION TIME ON THE CONVERSION OF NITRILE TO AMIDE.

Solvent : 35 cc water, Nitrile : Pyridine-3-carbonitrile
5 gm., Catalyst manganese dioxide 1 gm.

No. of obs.	Reaction Time, hr.	Yield of Amide (wt. %)
1.	2.5 hr	40
2.	4	79
3.	5	108
4.	8	85

Catalyst/substrate ratio :

Table 6 represents the result of the experiments carried out with different ratios of weight of the catalyst

(in gms) to the moles of feed. It is observed that the yield of nicotinamide from pyridine 3 carbonitrile is not appreciably affected in the range 0.025 to 0.1.

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF THE W/F, ON THE CONVERSION OF NITRILE TO AMIDE.

Solvent-water 35 cc. Catalyst manganese dioxide, Nitrile (5 g.) Pyridine-3-carbonitrile, Temp. 100°C, reaction time 5 hrs.

No. of obs.	W/F.	Yield of Amide (wt. %)
1.	0.1018	87.5
2.	0.1006	96.24
3.	0.0502	93.7
4.	0.0250	87.5

Mechanism of action of Nickel :

When ortho-nitro benzonitrile was hydrogenated either in the liquid or vapour phase³, it was reported that a considerable quantity of orthoaminobenzamide was formed by the hydration of nitrile group. It has been presumed⁴ that the hydrogenating activity of the nickel catalyst is largely depressed by poisoning with amine group produced by the reduction of nitrogroup and that the nitrile group is hydrated with the water produced by the hydrogenolysis of nitro group originally present in the system. The present investigation shows that such is the case since the ability of the nickel catalyst to effect the hydration of nitrile group has been proved.

It is noteworthy that nitrile group, of basic character such as Pyridine 3-carbonitrile and Pyridine-4-carbonitrile give good yields of amide, whereas those of acidic character such as *p*-hydroxy benzonitrile gives no hydration product.

According to the studies of reaction mechanism of the hydrolysis of nitriles with acid or alkali⁷, the hydration has been assumed to be initiated at the carbon atom of the nitrile group, endowed with a carbonium ion character. In the catalytic hydration of nitriles, the reaction may be similarly initiated at the carbon atom attached to the basic sites of the catalyst.

Mechanism of action of manganese dioxide catalyst :

The role of manganese-dioxide in the reaction has not yet been elucidated. It may be postulated that since the reaction is biphasic, adsorption of the substrate is followed by hydrolysis and subsequent desorption of the product. The more easily hydrolysable compounds, are however, those that would be expected to form the most stable carbonium ion⁵, which may perhaps play an important role in the reaction mechanism.

* (1) Reduction of Potassium permanganate with manganous salts.

(2) Reaction of Manganese acetate with potassium persulphate.

Fig. 1. I.R. Spectra of variously prepared MnO_2 samples in the region 2400 cm^{-1} – 4000 cm^{-1} .

I—I.R. Spectrum of MnO_2
 F—I.R. Spectrum of MnO_2
 H—I.R. Spectrum of MnO_2

The peculiar effectiveness of manganese dioxide may in part be related to the fact that as ordinarily prepared by precipitation it is a "non stoichiometric" compound, has oxygen content slightly less than that corresponding to the dioxide⁶, and also contains water (3-4%) which

can not be removed thermally without some further loss of oxygen. The water is probably present as hydroxyl group linked to manganese. To confirm this statement I. R. of different samples of MnO_2 prepared by different methods were recorded and in some cases broad bands in the region $3100\text{--}3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were observed (Fig. 1) indicative of the presence of -O-H groups. The formation of hydroxylated intermediate may be assisted, if not caused, by these hydroxyl groups in the dioxide resulting in the formation of amides.

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